

Maternal Alcohol and Smoking: Effects on Breastfeeding Initiation and Continuation: A Scoping Review

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Contents

PubMed

Scopus

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DATABASE SEARCHED / DATE		SEARCH STRING	RESULTS
PUBMED September 2024	1	"Nursing women"[Title/Abstract] OR "nursing mothers"[Title/Abstract] OR "breastfeeding women"[Title/Abstract] OR Pregnant [Title/Abstract] OR "pregnant women"[Title/Abstract] OR "lactating	801,093

		mother"[Title/Abstract] OR infant*[Title/Abstract] OR neonate*[Title/Abstract] OR "newborn babies"[Title/Abstract]	
	2	("Alcohol" [Title/Abstract] OR "smoking "[Title/Abstract] OR smoking*[Title/Abstract] OR "alcohol intake"[Title/Abstract] AND ("breastfeeding"[Title/Abstract] OR lactation[Title/Abstract] OR "infants" OR "children" [Title/Abstract] OR "infant"))	35,653
	3	1 AND 2	10,862
	4	("Exclusive breastfeeding"[Title/Abstract] OR "breastfeeding initiation"[Title/Abstract] OR "breastfeeding continuation" OR "Exclusive breastfeeding")) [Title/Abstract])	6,983
	5	3 AND 4	197
Science Direct November 2024		("Nursing women" OR "nursing mothers" OR pregnant OR lactation* OR neonate*) AND ("alcohol" OR "alcohol use" OR smoking* OR smoking use) AND ("breastfeeding" OR "human milk") AND ((exclusive OR initiation OR continuation OR "infant"))	32,400
	Time period	1997-2024	60

Scopus January 2024		TI (("Nursing women" OR "nursing mothers" OR "breastfeeding women" OR Pregnant OR "pregnant women" OR "lactating mother" OR infants OR neonates OR "newborn babies")) AND (alcohol OR "drug use" OR smoking* OR "alcohol use" OR alcohol intake OR infant development OR "smoke exposure") AND ("breastfeeding" OR lactation OR "human milk") AND ((exclusive OR initiation OR continuation OR "infant exposure"))	297
		TOTAL RETRIEVED	297+197+60 = 553
		DUPLICATES	46
		TOTAL FOR SCREENING	554